

MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES

VI SİNİFLƏRDƏ RİYAZİYYAT FƏNNİNİN “STATİSTİKA VƏ EHTİMAL” MƏZMUN XƏTTİ ÜZRƏ MATERİALLARININ TƏDRİSİNDƏ GÖZLƏNİLMƏSİ ZƏRURİ OLAN PROSESSUAL MƏQAMLAR

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PROCEDURAL POINTS THAT MUST BE EXPECTED IN TEACHING MATERIALS ON "STATISTICS AND PROBABILITY" CONTENT LINE AT MATHEMATICS SUBJECT IN THE VI CLASSES

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Xülasə

Məqalədə Riyaziyyat fənnində “Statistika və ehtimal məzmun xətti” müxtəlif ədədi kəmiyyətlərin orta qiymətinin təyin edilməsi və hesablanması, seçim zamanı təsadüflərin nəzərə alınması, toplanmış materialların təsnifatı və qrafiklər üzrə təhlilin aparılması kimi məsələlərin şagirdlər tərəfindən öyrənilməsi məqsədilə VI sinifdə reallaşdırılmalı olan bilik və bacarıqların (gözlənilən nəticələrin) mündərəcəsi təqdim edilir. VI sinifdə “Statistika və ehtimal məzmun xətti” üzrə materialların “Məlumatların toplanması”, “Seçilmiş məlumatın dəyişməsinə xarakterizə edən cədvəlin qurulması”, “Diaqram”, “Histoqram”, “Ədədi orta”, “Moda və median”, “Proqnozların verilməsi”, “Hadisələrin növünün müəyyən olunması”, “Azehtimallı və çoxehtimallı hadisələr”, “Mümkün halların sayı”, “Nisbətən mürəkkəb hadisələrdə əlverişli halların sayı” mövzuları vasitəsilə reallaşdırılmasının məqsədə uyğun olduğu göstərilir. İşdə elmi mənbələrdən və iş təcrübəsindən əldə olunmuş materialların ümumiləşməsi əsasında təqdim edilən mövzular üzrə tədris prosesinin həyata keçirilməsinin məzmun və strukturlunun interpretasiyası verilir.

Abstract

In the article, the knowledge and skills (expected results) that must be realized in the VI grade in order to learn by students such issues as "Statistics and probability content line" in the subject of Mathematics, such as determining and calculating the average value of various numerical quantities, taking into account coincidences during selection, classifying the collected materials and conducting analysis on graphs) content is presented. "Data collection", "Building a table characterizing the change of the selected data", "Diagram", "Histogram", "Numerical average", "Mode and median", "Giving forecasts", "Determining the type of events", "Low-probability and high-probability events", "Number of possible cases", It is shown that its implementation through the topics "number of favorable cases in relatively complex events" is appropriate for the purpose. In this work, the content and structure of the implementation of the educational process on the presented topics is given based on the generalization of the materials obtained from scientific sources and work experience.

Açar sözlər: məzmun xətti; statistika və ehtimal; məlumat; kəmiyyətin orta qiyməti; təsadüflər; ədədi orta, moda və median; səpələnmə diaqramı; histoqram; hadisə və hadisələrin növləri; azehtimallı və çoxehtimallı hadisələr; mürəkkəb hadisələr; əlverişli hallar; mümkün hallar; asılı və asılı olmayan hadisələr.

Keywords: content line; statistics and probability; information; average value of the quantity; coincidences; numerical mean, mode and median; scatter diagram; histogram; events and types of events; low-probability and high-probability events; complex events; favorable circumstances; possible cases; dependent and independent events.

The actuality of the subject. From the analysis and summarization of the observation and other research materials obtained during the last ten years, it is concluded that there are deficiencies both in the activity

of students and in the system of implementing the teaching process of teachers in the "Statistics and Probability" content line and errors exist. There are many reasons for these real manifestations, among which the presence of "theoretical and technological gaps" in the formation of the methodical system of teaching in the mentioned content line has a special place. Here, the main mistake is not expecting the necessary procedural points in the methodical system of teaching. Despite what has been said, the relevance of the topic is claimed by us.

Interpretation of generalizations formed on the basis of materials collected on the subject. In the Framework Document of the Concept of General Education (National Curriculum) in the Republic of Azerbaijan, the curriculum as a "conceptual document that enables the effective organization, purposeful and consistent implementation of all activities related to the educational process" includes standards, the necessary minimum, requirements for the training of students, technology and assessment issues in its content. In fact, each of these issues is contained in the curriculum as its component, important components. It is expected that these components interact with each other, complement each other, and be its logical continuation. [1; 167]. There have been various approaches to modernizing the training process, which they are unique in terms of methodological systems. The elements of "goal, content, means, form of organization" were included in the structure of the training system in a different way with the functions of providing opportunities, in other words, they were included in the system corresponding to the changing content of the principles of training. Active/interactive learning model and its methodical system are preferred in general education schools currently operating in Azerbaijan, which is adequate to the Curriculum adopted for the implementation of education (see [10-12] for more information).

In the subject of mathematics, "Statistics and Probability content line" was included in order for the students to learn such issues as determining and calculating the average value of various numerical quantities, considering coincidences during selection, classifying the collected materials and conducting analysis on graphs. Through this content line, in elementary grades, the study of issues such as performing probability experiments, collecting data and depicting them graphically is ensured, in upper grades, a deeper study of statistics and its impact on everyday life, and the formation of judgment and decision-making experience based on the collected data are created.[6 ; 66-68]

A student who completed his education in the sixth form:

5.1. Collects, systematizes, analyzes and presents statistical information.

5.1.1. Formulates relevant questions to collect the necessary statistical data.

5.1.2. Constructs a table or diagram that characterizes the change of selected data according to certain characteristics.

5.1.3. Finds the mode, median, and mean of the collected numerical data.

5.1.4. Makes predictions based on data analysis.

5.2. Understands and applies concepts of probability.

5.2.1. It distinguishes between low-probability and high-probability events.

5.2.2. Finds the number of favorable cases in relatively complex cases.

As it can be seen, the educational activity of VI graders on the mentioned content lines is realized in the direction of two main standards - "Collects, systematizes, analyzes and presents the results of statistical information", "Understands and applies the concepts of probability". In which the standards for the subject of mathematics cover the content that is important for all students within the framework of the general education course, describe the mathematical comprehension abilities, knowledge and skills of students, determine the issues that every student in the country can and should learn in the field of mathematics, and prepare students for the next level of education. .

Each standard objective covers several expected learning outcomes defined according to the levels of general education. As it is emphasized in scientific sources, in the content standard, knowledge acts as the sides of the unit with activity. [3; 84-85]

The student can achieve the content of mathematics through various activities. During his activity, he makes judgments to solve problems, proves mathematical propositions, connects the obtained data, develops a general mathematical model and presents it in different ways. The specified stages of student activity in the process of mastering the content ensure that the acquired knowledge and skills are more solid and long-lasting. Scientific sources rightly emphasize that the level of realization of the expected results of the students' educational activity depends on the "teaching situation (or tasks), teaching operations, dialectical unity of control and evaluation elements". Educational activity is a type of human activity, a unique form of personality social activity, training is an important characteristic of educational activity. [2; 150].

The compilers of the mathematics subject program and the authors of the textbook are of the opinion that it is appropriate to implement the materials on "Statistics and probability content line" in the VI class on the topics listed below.

Data collection; Building a table that characterizes the change of the selected information; diagram; Histogram; Numerical mean, mode and median; Providing forecasts; Determination of the type of events; Low-probability and high-probability events; Number of possible cases; A favorable number of cases in relatively complex cases.

Based on scientific sources and our work experience, we consider it useful to apply the content and structured technological approach interpreted below in the implementation of the educational process on the mentioned topics.

1. About the points to be focused on in the teaching of the topic "Data collection".

Standard: 5.1.1. Formulates relevant questions to collect the necessary statistical data.

The greatest importance of learning the subject by students is that it gives them the ability to gather the necessary information for solving various problems.

Students are told that in every life situation, the right decision is made when the necessary information is available. Before making any decision, it is necessary to collect certain information. This information can be collected in various ways. In order to collect information, the problematic situation should be defined, the methods of information collection should be clarified, the questions that serve to collect information should be selected, it should be determined whether the collected information is true or not, etc.

The teacher declares that there is a special field of activity dealing with these issues. That field is called "Statistics". The teacher provides such information to the students about the field of employment of "Statistics": Statistics deals with the collection, processing, comparison and analysis of information. Its purpose is to help people solve certain problems.

In the process of teaching the subject, it is useful for students to be involved in the following research based on what has been mentioned. [7; 92-93]

Research 1. You want to sell newspapers in your spare time, but you can only devote a certain part of the day to this business. In order to make the right decision in each area, it is important to have certain information. What you need to determine to determine whether a newspaper selling business is possible:

- 1) Which newspapers sell the most? 2) What time of the day are the sales more?
- 3) In which part of the city should you organize a sale? 4) How should the value be set?
- 5) Is there competition in this field? And so on.

Research 2. You want to buy a quality computer at an affordable price. You need to have some information to make the right decision. This information may include:

- 1) Where are computers sold? 2) What is their selling price? 3) Which computer produced in the company? 4) How is its quality? 5) What guarantee does the company provide? 6) What is the quality of work of the guaranteeing firm? And so on. [4; 832-833]

The teacher asks the following question: To what extent does the information collected based on the questions help to make any decision?

Students' opinions are listened to.

In the process of teaching the subject, tasks are systematized according to the research question "What is the importance of formulating relevant questions for data collection?" and are offered to students in groups or groups (on worksheets).

After the groups have presented their work, ideas about the importance of formulating relevant questions in obtaining statistical information are summarized.

2. The points to be selected as a point of view on the topic "Building a table characterizing the change of the selected data".

Standard: 5.1.2. Constructs a table or diagram that characterizes the change of selected data according to certain characteristics.

Students are told that gathering information is not enough to make a certain decision. It is important to present the collected data in various forms for processing and analysis. This is the most commonly used form of presentation. But the schedule should be made in a convenient form. [7; 94]

Therefore, the teacher involves the students in the research activity related to the construction of the table in a convenient form and learns the opinions of the students about why the presented form of the table is convenient.

In the teaching of the topic, it is recommended to formulate the research question as follows: What is the importance of creating a table in presenting information?

Students can work in groups or pairs to conduct research. Here, the teacher can give students the opportunity to freely choose the area where they will collect information.

Example:

I group. "Guys, what kind of sport would you like to play? - answer the question and make a table. In what form is it convenient to give the table? (Each student can suggest his own table form).

Group II. In order to choose the class leader, it was necessary to conduct a survey among students and draw up a table reflecting the results of the survey. In your opinion, what questions should be included in the survey for the correct selection of the leader? Make a schedule.

Group III. "What kind of art would you like to have in the future? - systematize the answers to the survey and make a table. Determine what percentage of the entire class is the number of students who chose each art.

Discussion of group presentation. Each group makes a table by formulating relevant questions. The table form is demonstrated during the presentation and evaluated by the students. The assessment is based on the clarity, concreteness, purposeful construction of the questions put to the collection of information, etc. is taken into account. The originality of the selected table form is evaluated by the same rule.

At the end of the lesson, the teacher summarizes the opinions expressed about the importance of tables in collecting and presenting information, and notes the importance of presenting information in the form of tables.

3. Important points to be expected in the methodical system of teaching the "Diagram" subject.

Standard: 5.1.2. Constructs a table or diagram that characterizes the change of selected data according to certain characteristics.

It is reported that the forms of selection of the diagram, which is considered to be one of the forms of information presentation, should also be appropriate. Various diagram forms are presented to the students through the computer. Questions are asked that determine which diagram shapes students recognize. Examples of these forms are described by students on the board. The teacher summarizes the information that the students said about the types of diagrams and lists them sequentially.

Research is being conducted around the question "What is the importance of constructing a diagram in presenting information?" [5; 891]

In the process of teaching the subject, tasks are systematized according to the research question "What is the importance of constructing a diagram in the presentation of information?" and are offered to students in groups or groups (on worksheets).

The construction of the diagram can be given in one of the office programs on the computer. The teacher gives his opinion about the importance of the diagram in collecting and presenting information, summarizes what has been learned about the forms of the diagram and when it is convenient to use which form.

It is recommended to conduct the assessment in the lesson according to the levels reflected below.

Level I: Has difficulty constructing a diagram that characterizes the change in data.

Level II: Constructs a diagram that characterizes the change of information with a specific instruction.

Level III: Constructs an appropriate diagram that characterizes the change in information.

4. Important points to be expected in the methodical system of teaching "Histogram" subject.

Standard: 5.1.2. Constructs a table or diagram that characterizes the change of selected data according to certain characteristics.

As a type of chart, it is considered appropriate to talk about the histogram separately. So, this type of diagram is more convenient for characterizing the change of information between certain intervals. In class V, students learned to construct a histogram for some data. Here, it is recommended that students construct a histogram of variable data with the help of Microsoft Word office software. [4; 835]

In the lesson, the research question can be formulated as follows: In what cases is it convenient to build a histogram?

Students are divided into pairs for the purpose of research. They build the histogram according to the task both by hand and on the computer in the worksheets given to them.

At the end of the lesson, the teacher lists the cases in which the histogram is constructed. Emphasizes the role of the histogram in presenting data that varies over intervals.

5. Summary of the methodical system for teaching the subject "Numerical mean, mode and median".

Standard: 5.1.3. Finds the mode, median, and mean of the collected numerical data.

The teacher asks the students questions in order to ask them what they know from the lower grades about finding the numerical mean, the largest difference, the mode and the median of the given numbers. Students' answers are listened to.

Students should know that finding the numerical mean, the largest difference, the mode and the median (statistical mean) of a numerical series is of great importance for data analysis and drawing conclusions.

The teacher gives a detailed explanation about the numerical mean, mode and median. Here, the teacher can explain to the students that the concept of the

largest difference indicates the length of the numerical sequence. It should be clarified to the students that "the length of the numerical sequence" refers to the difference between the largest and the smallest number participating in the numerical sequence. In the process of teaching the subject, students should be informed about bimodal numbers.

In the lesson, the research question is defined as follows: What is the role of finding the numerical mean, mode, and median in data analysis?

In the process of teaching the subject, the tasks are systematized according to the research question "What is the role of finding the numerical mean, mode, and median in the analysis of data?" and are offered to students in groups or groups (on worksheets).

At the end of the lesson, the teacher should note that finding the numerical mean, mode and median, based on the results of the research, plays a major role in solving many vital issues. It emphasizes the importance of finding these quantities in making any decision, in comparison, in examining how realistic the results are.

6. Summarizing notes on the methodical system of teaching the topic "Giving forecasts".

Standard: 5.1.4. Makes predictions based on data analysis.

The teacher addresses the class with the question "How can you tell whether any event will happen or not?". Students' opinions are listened to. Then the teacher clarifies the question: "How is it predicted that the weather will be sunny tomorrow?" Again, students' opinions are listened to. "What other events can be predicted?" is voiced by the teacher. There are discussions about how to make predictions about earthquakes, hurricanes, strong winds, and the speed of sea waves (it is appropriate to prepare a presentation on a computer).

The teacher addresses the class and gives information on how to make predictions of simpler events. He says that forecasts are made based on data analysis.

The teacher reminds the students that in the previous lessons we dealt with the issues of gathering, processing and presenting information. He offers them to discuss about making predictions.

In the lesson, in the text below, a research question is asked: Why is it necessary to make a forecast?

The teacher informs the students about the functions of the forecast.

In the process of teaching the subject, the tasks are systematized according to the research question "Why is it necessary to make a forecast?" and are offered to students in groups or groups (on worksheets). [5; 893]

It is recommended to conduct the assessment in the lesson according to the levels reflected below.

Level: Has difficulty making predictions by analyzing data.

Level II: Analyzes the data and makes a close prediction.

Level III: Freely predicts by analyzing data. [7; 99]

7. Interpretation on the topic "Determining the type of events".

Standard: 5.2.1. Determines the number of possible outcomes of trials.

The teacher brings to the students' attention that when predicting whether any event will happen in life, we often use such expressions: "it is impossible", "most likely...", "you can be one hundred percent sure that...". Thus, we draw certain conclusions based on the analyzed data. You know that there are three types of events: "probable event", "impossible event", "random event". An event that will definitely happen based on given conditions is called a probable event. An event that will never happen under given conditions is called an impossible event. An event that either happens or does not happen based on given conditions is called a random event.

The teacher interprets various events, students' opinions about the possibility or impossibility of this or that event are heard (those events can be displayed on the computer in the form of slides).

By discussing several events, the characteristics of probable, improbable and random events are consciously perceived by the students. The research question in the lesson is as follows: How is the type of event determined?

In the process of teaching the subject, tasks are systematized according to the research question "How is the type of event determined?" and are offered to students in groups or groups (on worksheets).

It is recommended to conduct the assessment in the lesson according to the levels reflected below.

Level I: Makes mistakes when determining the type of event.

Level II: Identifies the type of event, but has difficulty explaining the idea.

Level III: Freely defines the type of event.

8. Points to be focused on in the methodical system of teaching the topic "Low-probability and high-probability events".

Standard: 5.2.2. It distinguishes between low-probability and high-probability events.

The teacher gives examples of events that are more or less likely to happen:

1. A coin has two sides, and the event of any of the heads falling is equally likely, because both of these faces are equally likely to fall.

2. There are 3 rollerball pens in the box. One of these pens is red and two are blue. Shamkhal took a pencil without looking at the box. This time:

a) the appearance of a blue pencil; b) Is the event of the red pen coming out equally likely? [8; 173]

Each event is discussed.

The research question in the lesson can be formulated as follows: When are events less likely or more likely?

The class is divided into groups for the purpose of research. In the worksheets given to each group, the teacher gives tasks in such a way that according to that task, the students distinguish the events that are more or less likely to happen.

At the end of the lesson, the teacher should make a generalization about low-probability and high-probability, equally probable events.

It is recommended to conduct the assessment in the lesson according to the levels reflected below.

Level I: Makes mistakes when determining the probability and probability of an event.

Level II: Determines the probability and probability of an event, but has difficulty explaining its meaning.

Level III: Freely correctly determines the probability and probability of an event.

9. A laconic comment on the topic "Number of possible cases".

Standard: 5.2.1. Determines the number of possible outcomes of trials.

The teacher poses the following problem to the students: how many two-digit numbers can be written using each of the numbers 0, 2, and 5 once? Time is given for research. All possible cases are written on the board: 20, 25, 50, 52. As you can see, the number of possible cases here is four.

Another task is used and the number of possible cases is determined as follows:

□ Aykhan forgot the code of the entrance door, but he remembered that it consisted of four digits - "0" and "1". How many cases does he have to look at before he can open the door?

Solution: By default, the door code consists of four digits, and only the digits "0" and "1" are included in the writing. So, in writing the code, there can be three "0" and one "1", two "0" and two "1", and three "1" and one "0".

Each case is investigated:

1) Case with three "0" and one "1": 0001; 0010; 0100; 1000 - 4 cases;

2) Case with two "0" and two "1": 0011 ; 0101; 0110; 1010; 1100; 1001 - 6 cases;

3) Case with one "0" and three "1": 0111; 1011; 1101; 1110 - 4 cases.

Thus, it is determined that there are a total of 14 possible outcomes.

A point to note: Students sometimes find it difficult to understand the expression "possible cases". For this reason, the teacher should work as much as possible so that the students understand the meaning of this expression for each observed event. [4; 838]

It is advisable to apply the following research question in the lesson: How to determine the number of possible cases for an event to occur or not?

In the process of teaching the subject, the tasks are systematized according to the research question "How to determine the number of possible cases for an event to happen or not?" and are offered to students in groups or groups (on worksheets).

Generalization and inference: The teacher shares his ideas about methods of determining the number of possible outcomes in various events.

It is recommended to conduct the assessment in the lesson according to the levels reflected below. [7; 104-105]

Level I: Difficulty in determining the number of possible cases of an event occurring.

Level II: Determines the number of possible cases of occurrence of the event with the direction of the teacher.

Level III: Descriptively defines the number of possible occurrences of an event.

10. About the teaching of the topic "Number of favorable cases in relatively complex events".

Standard: 5.2.3. Finds the number of favorable cases in relatively complex cases.

In the previous lesson, the number of possible cases of occurrence of the event was investigated, the students acquired sufficient knowledge and skills. During this lesson, among the possible cases, the cases that are favorable for the occurrence of the event and their number are examined.

The following event (example) is called by the teacher, and the number of possible outcomes and the number of favorable cases of the occurrence of this event are discussed and clarified:

Research 1. What is the number of favorable occasions when a die is rolled with a score greater than 4?

Solution: There are 6 possible cases in a single roll of the dice. Since the scores greater than 4 are 5 and 6, the number of favorable cases is 2.

Research 2. Two dice are rolled. Find the number of favorable cases for the event that the sum of the points falling face up is 7.

The solution: We know that there are 36 possible cases when two dice are tossed simultaneously. Those with a total of 7 points falling on the upper face: (1,6); (2,5); (3,4); (4,3); (5,2); (6,1) becomes. The event that the total number of points is 7 is considered favorable and their number is 6. [8;178]

In this lesson, it is recommended to formulate the research question as follows: How to determine the number of favorable cases in complex events?

In the process of teaching the subject, the tasks "How to determine the number of favorable cases in complex events?" - systematized according to the research question and is offered to the students in groups or groups (on worksheets).

Generalization and conclusion: The teacher summarizes how the number of favorable cases is determined in relatively complex cases.

It is recommended to conduct the assessment in the lesson according to the levels reflected below.

Level I: Difficulty in determining the number of favorable occasions for an event to occur.

Level II: Determines the number of favorable cases of the occurrence of the event with the direction of the teacher.

Level III: Descriptively defines the number of favorable conditions for an event to occur.

Small summative assessment criteria

1. Apply appropriate questions to collect statistical data.

2. Builds a table that characterizes the change of information.

3. Builds a diagram that characterizes the change of information.

4. Finds the mean, mode and median.

5. Makes a forecast based on data analysis.

6. Defines the type of event.

7. Determines whether the event is unlikely or highly probable.

8. Determines the number of possible cases of occurrence of the event.

9. Determines the number of favorable cases in relatively complex events.[5; 897]

Small summative assessment tasks[8; 212]

Surname: _____ First name: _____

Number of correct answers: _____

Number of wrong answers: _____ Score: _____

1. To gather information about what your classmates will be doing during the summer holidays, formulate some relevant questions:

1. _____
2. _____
3. _____
4. _____
5. _____

2. The audience in the movie theater consisted of people in the age range of 15% 8 – 12% 12 – 16% 16 – 20% 20 – 24 and the rest. Determine the number of people in the age range 24-28. Construct a histogram based on the data.

3. Show the data given in the task in the form of a table and a pie chart.2 –

4. Based on the given table, which athlete can be predicted to win the next competition?

Athletes	He won the victory number of games	That he was defeated number of games	The result
I	12	12	
II	8	16	
III	11	14	
IV	15	10	

